

ISic0831

I.Sicily inscription 0831

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

2015.07.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Amphitheatre

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 194

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ΝΕΑΝ[---]
2. [---]ΔΞΟΝΤΑ[---]
3. [---][ἰδία]ι δαπάν[αι---
4. [---]ΣΣΑΙΣΟ[---]
5. [---][ΛΓ[---

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492456

EDCS 39101982

PHI 140302

PHI 332967

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0011 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0790
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0738.4
- undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique.* At 1995.0029
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5369b
- Ferrua, A 1938-1939. Note di epigrafia cristiana siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano.* 4-5: 19-37. At 22-23
- Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 92-93 no.4 fig.12

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0831. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339606>